

1 **The winter North Pacific teleconnection in response to ENSO and the MJO**
2 **in operational subseasonal forecasting models is too weak**

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15 ABSTRACT: Teleconnection patterns associated with the Madden-Julian oscillation (MJO) and
16 El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) impact weather and climate phenomena in the Pacific-North
17 American region and beyond, and therefore accurately simulating these teleconnections is of im-
18 portance for seasonal and subseasonal forecasts. Systematic biases in boreal mid-winter ENSO
19 and MJO teleconnections are found in 8 subseasonal to seasonal (S2S) forecast models over the
20 Pacific-North America region. All models simulate an anomalous 500-hPa geopotential height
21 response that is too weak. This overly weak response is associated with overly weak subtropical
22 upper level convergence and a too-weak Rossby wave source in most models, and in several mod-
23 els also with a biased subtropical Pacific jet which affects the propagation of Rossby waves. In
24 addition to this overly weak response, all models also simulate ENSO teleconnections that reach
25 too far poleward towards Alaska and Northeastern Russia. The net effect is that these models likely
26 under-estimate the impacts associated with the MJO and ENSO over Western North America, and
27 suffer from a reduction in skill from what could be achieved.

1. Introduction

El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) dominates the interannual variability of the tropical Pacific ocean and atmosphere (Timmermann et al. 2018, and references therein). During its warm phase (El Niño, hereafter EN), sea surface temperatures (SSTs) in the eastern and central tropical Pacific increase, the trade winds weaken, and tropical precipitation and the upwelling branch of the Walker Circulation shifts eastwards towards the Central Pacific. Opposite-signed changes occur during the cool phase (La Niña, hereafter LN). While ENSO is driven mainly by coupled air-sea processes within the tropical Indo-Pacific, teleconnections of ENSO extend to the rest of the world via changes in the large-scale atmospheric circulation (Taschetto et al. 2020). These teleconnections to the North Pacific are invaluable for seasonal climate prediction over North America and Eurasia (Horel and Wallace 1981; Ropelewski and Halpert 1987; Zhang et al. 1996; Shukla et al. 2000; Wang et al. 2000; DeWeaver and Nigam 2004; Brönnimann 2007; Garfinkel et al. 2013; Scaife et al. 2017; Garfinkel et al. 2019b; Weinberger et al. 2019; Taschetto et al. 2020), and begin with a subtropical North Pacific ridge and deepened Aleutian low (Tim et al. 2017).

The physical underpinning of the extratropical Northern Hemisphere atmospheric circulation response to ENSO can be understood using the theoretical framework of poleward-propagating Rossby waves forced by anomalous upper-tropospheric tropical divergent outflow and subsequent subtropical convergence (Hoskins and Karoly 1981; Held and Kang 1987; Sardeshmukh and Hoskins 1988; Hoskins and Ambrizzi 1993; Trenberth et al. 1998; Garfinkel and Hartmann 2010; Scaife et al. 2017). After the wave reaches the extratropics, it interacts with the extratropical background flow that can modify its strength and direction of propagation. Wave-mean flow interactions can refract or duct the waves, energy can be extracted from the exit region of the subtropical East Asian jet, and synoptic eddies can interact with and either weaken or strengthen this wavetrain (Simmons et al. 1983; Branstator 1985; Hoskins and Ambrizzi 1993; Jin and Hoskins 1995; Held et al. 1989; Harnik et al. 2010). The net of these interactions is the forced response to ENSO, and this forced response forms a bedrock for seasonal forecasting of weather and climate extremes (Goddard and Gershunov 2020).

Models need to represent these processes accurately in order to maximize the prediction skill associated with ENSO, however biases can lead to less than the maximum possible skill being achieved. Model biases in the extratropical mean state can lead to biased teleconnections even

58 for an identical tropical perturbation (Ting and Sardeshmukh 1993), while biases in the tropical
59 mean state can lead to a poor representation of the ENSO SST anomalies and tropical precipitation
60 response (Spencer and Slingo 2003; Kim et al. 2014; Ham and Kug 2015; Bayr et al. 2018, 2019;
61 Ferrett et al. 2020; Liu et al. 2021).

62 The forced response due to ENSO is superposed on internal atmospheric variability. If the sam-
63 ple size of observed and modeled ENSO events is sufficiently large, then the effect of internal
64 atmospheric noise can be minimized, revealing biases in the forced response. In reality, the lim-
65 ited record length of the observed response to ENSO necessarily implies that the “true” forced
66 response to ENSO is, to some degree, unknown (Garfinkel et al. 2013; Deser et al. 2017). Sta-
67 tistical resampling techniques suggest that error-bars on the forced response for events over the
68 past century are of similar magnitude to the forced response itself (e.g. Figure 3 of Deser et al.
69 2017). This uncertainty on the magnitude of the forced response leads to difficulties in ascertaining
70 whether free-running climate models are biased in their extratropical response to ENSO, and thus
71 whether impacts are misrepresented (Deser et al. 2018; Garfinkel et al. 2019b; Weinberger et al.
72 2019). Put another way, there is no reason to expect similarly phased random internal variability
73 in a free-running model and in observations, and hence it is unclear to what extent the composite
74 mean response to ENSO either in a model or in observations reflects the true response to ENSO
75 vs. the random superposition of internal atmospheric circulation anomalies on the forced ENSO
76 response. That being said, systematic model biases do appear to be present in models participating
77 in the coupled model intercomparison project (CMIP): the North Pacific low is too weak close
78 to North America and too strong in the subtropical Central and West Pacific in CMIP6 models
79 (Figure 2 of Fasullo et al. 2020), though in previous CMIP generations the dominant bias was a
80 too-weak teleconnection (Weare 2013) even as the ENSO events themselves extend too far to the
81 west in most models and are too strong in many models (Ham and Kug 2015). An additional bias
82 is that the ENSO teleconnection peaks in February in models, instead of in January (Figure 1 of
83 Chen et al. 2020) mirroring the bias in the decay of SST anomalies during ENSO events (Liu et al.
84 2021), though even the prescribed SST simulations considered by Chen et al. (2020) suffer from
85 the delayed-teleconnection bias.

86 Tropical convection on timescales shorter than ENSO, namely due to the Madden Julian Os-
87 cillation (MJO), also can drive a North Pacific response via a mechanistically similar pathway

88 (Seo and Son 2012; Lukens et al. 2017; Seo and Lee 2017). Specifically, the MJO can drive
89 weather extremes in the extratropics by launching poleward propagating Rossby waves (Cassou
90 2008; L’Heureux and Higgins 2008; Lin et al. 2009; Johnson and Feldstein 2010; Yoo et al. 2012;
91 Garfinkel et al. 2012b, 2014; Riddle et al. 2013; Henderson et al. 2017; Goss et al. 2018; Wang
92 et al. 2020b). When anomalous MJO convection is in the West Pacific (MJO phases 6 and 7 as
93 diagnosed by the Wheeler and Hendon (2004) index), the North Pacific low is deepened. These
94 teleconnections are systematically too strong and far to the east in days 5 to 9 in CMIP models
95 (Wang et al. 2020b,a), but with substantial intermodel spread.

96 An alternative technique to assessing whether models are systematically biased in their response
97 to ENSO and the MJO is to use initialized reforecasts. Such reforecasts are initialized with ob-
98 served sea surface temperatures and the atmospheric state (including synoptic variability), and as
99 they are intended to be useful for forecasting operationally, they can be compared directly to ob-
100 served variability during the predicted lead time. Hence, they are initialized with, and meant to
101 include, the “internal variability” that clouds the picture when considering biases in ENSO tele-
102 connections in climate models. Furthermore, it is crucial that operational forecasts represent these
103 teleconnections reliably in order to maximize skill on subseasonal to seasonal timescales (Vitart
104 2017).

105 The Subseasonal-to-Seasonal (S2S) Prediction project (Vitart et al. 2017) has recently made
106 available a large number of hindcasts covering the past several decades. This work uses these
107 hindcasts to revisit the development of biases in ENSO teleconnections in early- to mid- winter,
108 and the implications of these biases for MJO teleconnections. After describing the data in Section
109 2, the biases are presented in Section 3. Possible causes of these biases are presented in Section 3,
110 and implications for the MJO are presented in section 4.

111 **2. Data and Methods**

112 *a. Data sources*

113 The fidelity of tropics-to-extratropics teleconnections is examined in models that have con-
114 tributed to the S2S Prediction project (Vitart et al. 2017). Of the eleven model which uploaded
115 data when this study was conducted, we focus on the eight modeling centers which include output
116 to at least week six to allow for model biases to develop. These models are: the Australian Bureau

Table 1: S2S Model experiments chosen

model (ensemble members)	years	reforecasts analyzed	vertical levels	model top
CMA - BCC-CPS-S2Sv1 (4)	1999-2014	6 per month	40	0.5hPa
NCEP (4)	1999-2010	9 per month	64	0.02hPa
ECMWF - CY46R1 (11)	2000-2018	4-5 per month	91	0.01hPa
BoM (33)	1981-2013	6 per month	17	10hPa
UKMO (7)	1993-2016	4 per month	85	85km
KMA (3)	1991-2010	4 per month	85	85km
Meteo France - CNRM-CM 6.1(10)	1993-2017	3-5 per month	91	0.01hPa
HMCR (10)	1985-2010	4-5 per month	28	5 hPa

TABLE 1.

117 of Meteorology (BoM), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF),
 118 the China Meteorological Administration (CMA), the United Kingdom Met. Office (UKMO),
 119 the National Center for Environmental Prediction (NCEP), the Korean Meteorological Agency
 120 (KMA), Hydrometeorological Centre of Russia (HMCR), and Météo-France (CNRM). We down-
 121 loaded hindcasts for the operational model in use during the winter of 2019/2020 for all models
 122 (for ECMWF, this is CY46R1). For the ECMWF model we downloaded only one reforecast each
 123 week, and for the NCEP model we only downloaded 9 reforecasts each month, for consistency
 124 with the data availability from the rest of the models. Table 1 summarizes the reforecasts analyzed
 125 in this study. ERA-interim reanalysis is used as the atmospheric reference to which forecast sys-
 126 tems are compared (Dee et al. 2011), and NOAA v2 daily sea surface temperatures are used for
 127 the oceanic state (Huang et al. 2021).

128 We consider reforecasts initialized in December during EN (Nino3.4 index exceeding 0.5K) vs
 129 those initialized in La Niña (LN; Nino3.4 index less than -0.5K), with the difference between these
 130 composites hereafter referred to as the “response to ENSO”. There are not enough ENSO events
 131 over the time period covered by the S2S archive in order to consider EN and LN separately (Deser
 132 et al. 2017; Garfinkel et al. 2019b), and hence we focus only on the EN minus LN difference.
 133 We focus on weekly averages as a function of week after initialization. A two-tailed difference of
 134 means Student-t test is used to assess the statistical significance of the difference between EN and
 135 LN composites, and the null hypothesis is that there is no difference between the two composites.
 136 For the observed response, each year is treated as one degree of freedom. In our figures showing
 137 the modeled response, we treat each hindcast ensemble member as a separate degree of freedom
 138 as we focus on the response beyond the first week after internal variability has already led to dif-

139 **ferences among the ensemble members; accounting for the correlation among different ensemble**
140 **members at these later lags has essentially no effect on the regions marked as significant.**

141 We then consider how biases develop in the models, defined as the difference between the ENSO
142 response in a model vs. that in observations. Note that each modeling center has made available
143 reforecasts from different years, and hence the specific ENSO events we analyze differ among the
144 models, and further the initialization dates differ among the models even for a given year. It is
145 therefore necessary to separately composite the observations according to the actual initializations
146 used for each model in order to meaningfully compare the modeled and observed responses to
147 ENSO.

148 The statistical significance of biases (differences between the hindcasts and ERA-I) in the re-
149 sponse to ENSO are computed via a Monte Carlo resampling technique as follows. Taking the
150 500hPa geopotential height (Z500) response to ENSO for initializations in December in ECMWF
151 as an example,

- 152 • Step 1: We randomly select December initializations from the full ECMWF hindcast ensem-
153 ble to match the number of actual EN and LN initializations without regard to the actual
154 ENSO phase, without allowing the same initialization to be placed in both the EN and LN
155 fictitious samples, and without computing the ensemble mean.
- 156 • Step 2: We then compute the difference in Z500 between the means of these fictitious EN and
157 LN samples, both for ECMWF and for the corresponding dates in ERA-I reanalysis.
- 158 • Step 3: We then compute the difference in Z500 between the ECMWF and ERA-I responses
159 for these fictitious composites.
- 160 • Step 4: Steps 1 through 3 are repeated 1000 times, with different initializations randomly
161 selected for the fictitious EN and LN composites. We then compute the bottom and top 2.5%
162 quantiles of the difference between the ECMWF and ERA-I without making any assumption
163 on the nature of the distribution, to which we compare the actual difference between ECMWF
164 and ERA-I. For this resampling test, each ensemble member is treated separately, however
165 our figures show the ensemble mean response.

166 The representation of the forced response to ENSO in a given model can be approximated from
167 the response averaged over many initializations and ensemble members. Our focus in this paper is

168 on week-6 teleconnections, which is late enough for any peculiarities of the initial condition to be
 169 mostly lost and the teleconnection to reflect model skill rather than persistence. We chose to focus
 170 on December initializations in order to understand the development of biases as the North Pacific
 171 response intensifies into mid-winter, though the North Pacific response is already evident though
 172 weak in December.

173 A similar procedure is followed for MJO teleconnections. Specifically, the response to the MJO
 174 is computed by comparing reforecasts initialized in November through February during phases 4
 175 and 5 and with amplitude exceeding 1 vs those initialized during phases 1 and 8 and with amplitude
 176 exceeding 1, as defined using the MJO index of Wheeler and Hendon (2004). The bias in a model
 177 is computed by comparing the MJO response in the model to that in observations. All other
 178 methodological details are as described for ENSO.

179 *b. Diagnostics*

180 We now describe the diagnostics used to understand biases in the response to ENSO and MJO.
 181 The seeding of Rossby waves by tropical rainfall is diagnosed using the Rossby wave source
 182 (RWS) of Sardeshmukh and Hoskins (1988). Expressing the horizontal wind as the sum of its
 183 rotational (ψ) and divergent (χ) components, the Rossby wave source is calculated as

$$\text{RWS} = -\nabla \cdot (\chi \zeta) = -\zeta \nabla \cdot \chi - \chi \cdot \nabla \zeta \quad (1)$$

184 where ζ is the absolute vorticity. The RWS is a source term in the equation for absolute vorticity.
 185 Two physical processes contribute to the RWS: change of vorticity due to vortex stretching (first
 186 term) and advection of vorticity by the divergent part of the wind (second term). We compute
 187 these terms using daily data for each ensemble separately before averaging over ENSO phases
 188 and weeks. We focus on the RWS at 200hPa (cf. Scaife et al. 2017; Ferrett et al. 2020). Three
 189 models suffer from severely too weak RWS and divergence at 200hPa in their climatology (defined
 190 as the average over all available November through February hindcasts), let alone overly weak
 191 interannual variability, and the S2S archive has not made available adjacent pressure levels where
 192 the reanalysis RWS is still relatively strong. These three models are BoM, CMA, and HMCR, and
 193 Supplemental Figure S1-3 shows the climatological 200hPa RWS and divergence for these models
 194 in the first few days after initialization to demonstrate this rapid decay. Hence in order to diagnose

195 biases in the convective response to ENSO/MJO, we also show the response of omega at 500hPa,
 196 as all models simulate a realistic climatology for this variable in the first week.

197 The impact of biases in the model upper-level zonal winds on Rossby wave propagation is diag-
 198 nosed by utilizing the stationary wavenumber K_s on Mercator coordinates (Karoly 1983; Hoskins
 199 and Ambrizzi 1993):

$$K_s = a \left(\frac{\beta_M}{\bar{u}_M} \right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

200 where the Mercator zonal wind \bar{u}_M is the time-mean 200-hPa zonal wind divided by the cosine
 201 of latitude, and a is the radius of Earth. The meridional gradient of absolute vorticity β_M is defined
 202 by

$$\beta_M = \left[2\Omega - \frac{1}{a} \left(\frac{1}{\cos \phi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \right)^2 (\cos^2 \phi \bar{u}_M) \right] \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{a} \quad (3)$$

203 where ϕ is latitude and Ω is Earth's rotational constant (following equations 2.12 and 2.13 of
 204 Hoskins and Ambrizzi 1993). Although the weekly-mean, ensemble-averaged zonal wind does
 205 not characterize the flow in a given ensemble member on a given day, previous work has found
 206 K_s to aid in understanding the behavior of stationary Rossby waves in observations and in GCMs
 207 (Seo and Lee 2017; Henderson et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2020b). On figures showing the Rossby
 208 wave source response to ENSO and biases in zonal wind, the $K_s = 3$ contour is overlaid, as this
 209 contour corresponds to a typical wavenumber of the anomalous convection in response to ENSO
 210 or the MJO, and the region of forbidden linear wave propagation (either because \bar{u}_M is easterly or
 211 because $\beta_M < 0$) is hatched in gray.

212 A stationary linear Rossby wave of wavenumber k is reflected at or will decay beyond the turning
 213 latitude in which $K_s = k$. Furthermore, Rossby waves are refracted toward regions where $K_s > k$,
 214 so that localized regions where K_s is relatively large, such as the westerly jets, act as waveguides
 215 (Hoskins and Ambrizzi 1993). Such a waveguide is formed by the West Pacific jet due to its
 216 strong meridional curvature ($\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \phi^2}$; Hoskins and Ambrizzi 1993; Henderson et al. 2017; Wang et al.
 217 2020b). Thus Rossby waves forced by ENSO or the MJO, especially those with zonal wavenumber
 218 4, propagate eastward along the jet and emanate at the jet exit region, while Rossby waves with
 219 zonal wavenumbers 1 and 2 can begin to propagate poleward immediately to the east of the region
 220 of forbidden propagation to the north of the jet following K_s contours 1 and 2 (Seo and Lee 2017),
 221 and thereby reach Alaska.

222 Regions of wave propagation can be diagnosed more quantitatively using wave ray tracing.
223 Wave rays represent energy dispersion trajectories as specified by the group velocity (Hoskins and
224 Karoly 1981; Lighthill 1978, pp 318). Here, we employ the ray equations based on wave theory
225 for a horizontal nonuniform background flow (Karoly 1983; Li and Nathan 1997; Li et al. 2015)
226 as described in detail in section 2b of Li et al. (2019). The ray trajectory is derived by integrating
227 equations (6)-(9) of Li et al. (2019) given the background wind, the starting latitude and longitude,
228 and the initial zonal wavenumber. The background wind is smoothed using spectral triangular
229 truncation at wavenumber 10 to remove small-scale disturbances. The ray is terminated when the
230 total wavenumber becomes larger than 40.

231 In addition to these effects concerning the location of extrema, Wang et al. (2020b) use a linear
232 baroclinic model to demonstrate that:

- 233 1. a stronger jet leads to stronger teleconnections, and vice versa when the jet is weaker. This is
234 consistent with ray theory in that the amplitude of stationary Rossby waves is proportional to
235 the speed of the mean zonal wind along a ray (Hoskins and Karoly 1981).
- 236 2. a southward jet shift leads to a stronger teleconnection amplitude than a northward jet shift.
237 This is reasonable as Rossby wave amplitude should be stronger when the strong absolute
238 vorticity gradient in the jet is placed closer to the subtropical convergent winds (Frederik-
239 sen and Webster 1988; Garfinkel and Hartmann 2010, as diagnosed by the second term of
240 Equation 1).

241 We will use these results in our interpretation of biases in ENSO and MJO teleconnections.

251 **3. Results**

252 We begin with the geopotential height response for initializations in EN as compared to LN in
253 forecast week 6 for each model and for the reanalysis subsampled to match the specific dates in-
254 cluded for each model (Figure 1). Consistent with previous work discussed in the introduction,
255 EN leads to a North Pacific low and a subtropical ridge. However this response is systematically
256 underestimated by all eight models. For five of the eight models the difference is statistically sig-
257 nificant (i.e. a null hypothesis of sampling variability can be rejected) as given by the resampling
258 test described in Section 2. The subtropical ridge is also too-weak in most models, and in all mod-
259 els the Southeastern United States trough is too-strong. Systematic and statistically-robust biases

242 FIG. 1. Response to ENSO in the sixth week after initialization in the December hindcast ensemble for the
 243 S2S models. For each model, the left column is for the responses in the S2S models, the middle column is for
 244 ERA-I subsampled to match the specific dates included in each composite for each model, and the right column
 245 the difference between the model and reanalysis responses (i.e. the bias). Difference-of-means between EN and
 246 LN that are statistically significant at the 95% confidence level as given by a Student-t test are denoted with dots
 247 on the left and middle columns; for the right column dots indicate that there is a significant difference between
 248 the modeled and observed response to ENSO as given by the resampling test described in Section 2. The black
 249 box indicates the region focused upon for Figure 2ab. The multi-model mean bias is shown in panel (i), and dots
 250 indicate that all models agree on the sign of the response (left and middle column) or of the bias (right column)

262 FIG. 2. Summary of the development of biases in response to ENSO, for initializations in Dec. (a-b) North
 263 Pacific low (boxed region on Figure 3). omega at 500hPa in the (c-d) tropical Pacific (red box on Figure 3);
 264 (e-f) subtropical Pacific (black box on Figure 3). Left column is for the S2S models and the right column is for
 265 ERA-I subsampled to match the specific dates included in each composite for each model. Difference-of-means
 266 between EN and LN that are statistically significant at the 95% confidence level as given by a Student-t test
 267 are denoted with dots on the left column; for the right column dots indicate that there is a significant difference
 268 between the modeled and observed response to ENSO as given by the Monte Carlo test described in Section 2.

260 are also evident over Eurasia as discussed in Garfinkel et al. (2019a), though our focus in this work
 261 is on the North Pacific sector.

269 The development of the North Pacific low is shown in Figure 2ab, which shows the difference
 270 in height between EN and LN in the boxed region of Figure 1. The observed North Pacific low

271 strengthens by more than a factor of two over the weeks covered by these hindcasts, however mod-
272 els struggle to represent the full magnitude of this increase in the strength of the low. Specifically,
273 while models generally are accurate in the first several weeks, by week six a systematic bias is ev-
274 ident: the North Pacific low is too weak in all models (Figure 1i and see Supplemental Figure S4).
275 **The envelope created by the ensemble spread of nearly all models does not encompass the reanaly-**
276 **sis response (Supplemental Figure S5), and only two individual ensemble members out of 82 total**
277 **across all models show a stronger response in the last forecasted week than that observed.** Biases
278 in late-winter are relatively smaller and not systematic across models (see the discussion section),
279 which we interpret to mean that the models are able to persist the ENSO related anomalies if they
280 are present upon initialization.

281 Such a bias in the development of the North Pacific response could arise from at least four
282 factors: biases in the sea surface temperatures, too weak variability in the North Pacific regardless
283 of the specific ENSO state, biased tropical convection in response to ENSO, or biases in the mean
284 state through which the anomalous wave-train propagates. Supplemental Figure S6, S7, and S8
285 show that the forecasting systems are able to maintain anomalous ENSO sea surface temperatures
286 for the duration of their subseasonal forecasts, and thus biases in teleconnections are not due to
287 biases in the oceanic component of the forecasting systems. Hence our focus in the rest of this
288 paper is on the atmospheric component. Supplemental Figure S9 considers the standard deviation
289 of 500hPa height in the boxed region of Figure 1 for each model in week 6 for each December
290 initialization as compared to corresponding dates in reanalysis data. It is evident that the models
291 simulate a realistic amount of variability in the North Pacific - **a two-tailed f-test of the ratio of the**
292 **variance between each model and its corresponding observational benchmark is not large enough**
293 **to reject a null hypothesis of no difference at the 5% confidence level for any model** - and hence
294 the too-weak teleconnection to ENSO is not a byproduct of a larger problem in the North Pacific
295 sector. The other two possible factors listed at the beginning of this paragraph - biases in the
296 convective response or in the background state - are, on the other hand, more relevant for the
297 too-weak teleconnection, as we demonstrate in Section 3a and 3b.

Dec initializations, wk:6
El Nino-La Nina omega500

299 FIG. 3. As in Figure 1 but for week 6 omega500. Note that HMCR has not uploaded omega to the S2S archive.
300 The red and black box indicates the region focused upon for Figure 2cd and 2ef respectively.

298 *a. Biases in convection*

301 We begin by considering the role of biases in convection and convective outflow. Figure 3 shows
302 the vertical (pressure) velocity, or omega, response at 500hPa to ENSO (EN minus LN). Upwelling
303 is evident over the tropical Central Pacific and downwelling over the Maritime Continent and sub-
304 tropical Central Pacific. This subtropical Central Pacific downwelling is of crucial importance for
305 the extratropical response, as this subtropical downwelling and the associated upper level conver-
306 gence is directly associated with the subtropical ridge (Hoskins and Karoly 1981; Sardeshmukh
307 and Hoskins 1988; Tim et al. 2017, see Supplemental Figure S10 for a more detailed discussion).
308 There is a wide diversity in the ability of models to simulate this response. BoM and NCEP both
309 simulate stronger tropical upwelling than observed, while UKMO and CMA simulate too-weak a
310 response. The biases are evident in all forecast weeks for most models (Figure 2cd, Supplemental
311 Figure S4b), and in addition to BoM and NCEP, KMA also simulates overly strong tropical up-
312 welling. Similar biases are also evident for subtropical subsidence (Figure 2ef and Supplemental

Dec initializations, wk:6
El Nino-La Nina div200

319 FIG. 4. As in Figure 1 but for week 6 divergence at 200hPa. The apparent lack of data for CMA and BoM
320 not a bug (Section 2b). A black box shows the region where rays are launched for Figures 8.

313 Figure S4c): KMA simulates too-strong subtropical downwelling in all weeks, while BoM and
314 NCEP simulate overly strong subsidence in most weeks. Other models tend to simulate too-weak
315 subtropical downwelling, and hence it is reasonable that their extratropical response should be
316 too weak as well. Specifically, Jiménez-Esteve and Domeisen (2019) find that the extratropical
317 response is linear with the magnitude of the upper level divergence anomalies, though not with the
318 sea surface temperature anomalies.

321 As discussed in Sardeshmukh and Hoskins (1988) and in Section 2, the forcing of extratropical
322 Rossby waves is sensitive to upper level divergent outflow and subtropical convergence, and we
323 now focus on the response of divergence at 200hPa to ENSO in Figure 4. In reanalysis divergence
324 is evident over the tropical Central Pacific and convergence in the subtropical Pacific, however
325 both extrema of this meridional dipole are too weak in all models, and significantly so in most
326 models. Even models which simulate a reasonable or too-strong response of omega at 500hPa to
327 ENSO (namely KMA, BoM, and NCEP; Figure 3) simulate too weak of an upper level divergence
328 response. The implication is that in these three models - KMA, BoM, and NCEP - the vertical

Dec initializations, wk:6
El Nino-La Nina RWS200

334 FIG. 5. As in Figure 1 but for week 6 RWS at 200hPa. The apparent lack of data for CMA and BoM is not a
 335 bug (Section 2b). The region of forbidden propagation for linear stationary Rossby waves in the climatology is
 336 shown with gray stippling, and the $K = 3$ contour is shown in magenta. A black box shows the region where
 337 rays are launched for Figures 8.

329 profile of the convection, and specifically upper tropospheric divergent outflow, is not represented
 330 accurately. The S2S archive does not include the 250hPa or 150hPa levels and hence we cannot
 331 assess other possible levels, and note that the reanalysis divergent outflow at 300hPa is weak. In
 332 contrast, biases in divergent outflow in ECMWF, CNRM, and UKMO are proportionate to biases
 333 in omega at 500hPa, implying a more reasonable convective profile.

338 This divergent outflow helps seed Rossby waves (Sardeshmukh and Hoskins 1988), and thus we
 339 show in Figure 5 the Rossby wave source defined as in Sardeshmukh and Hoskins (1988) for each
 340 model and the corresponding days in reanalysis in week 6. In reanalysis a positive RWS extrema
 341 is evident near 30N over the Western and Central Pacific, however this RWS anomaly is too weak
 342 in most models consistent with the too-weak divergence response to ENSO.

343 Figure 3, 4, 5 focus on week 6, however biases are similar in other weeks. We demonstrate this
344 for week 3 biases in all models in Supplemental Figure S11-S13, and the evolution of biases in
345 omega, divergence at 200hPa, and Rossby wave source in KMA in Supplemental Figure S14-S16.

346 While all models suffer from too-weak a convective forcing for the extratropical Rossby wave-
347 train, for some models the under-estimation is not statistically robust. Specifically the Rossby
348 wave source is of reasonable strength in CNRM, and only moderately too weak in ECMWF and
349 UKMO, yet all models nonetheless suffer from a biased teleconnection. We now consider whether
350 biases in the mean state may lead to such a biased teleconnection pattern.

351 *b. Extratropical mean state biases*

352 Biases in the extratropical response to ENSO can also be associated with a biased extratropical
353 mean state. The biases in the time mean zonal wind at 200hPa in week 6 for December initializa-
354 tions are shown in Figure 6. Figure 6 also includes the 40m/s and 60m/s isotachs, and the region
355 of forbidden propagation for linear stationary Rossby waves. Similar though weaker biases are
356 present in earlier weeks (Supplemental Figure S17). Figure 7 shows K_s as calculated by equation
357 2.

361 We first categorize the models by the nature of their biases:

- 362 1. NCEP, HMCR, and BoM suffer from a northward shifted and eastward extended jet, with
363 positive wind biases on the northward flank and negative wind biases on the equatorward flank
364 of the climatological jet. Consistent with this, the region of forbidden linear wave propagation
365 on the poleward flank of the jet (K_s undefined) extends further eastward for NCEP and BoM,
366 however for HMCR wind biases elsewhere overwhelm this effect.
- 367 2. CNRM and CMA suffer from a jet that does not extend far enough eastward and that is
368 equatorward shifted.
- 369 3. UKMO, ECMWF, and KMA have the smallest biases among the models, however all three
370 suffer from a jet that does not extend far enough eastward.

371 NCEP and BoM suffer from an eastward extended jet, and the North Pacific low is too close
372 to North America, with negative height anomalies near the coast and positive height anomalies
373 near the dateline (Figure 1). The linear theory of section 2b can casually connect these biases: the

358 FIG. 6. Biases in U 200hPa in week 6 (color contours), the 40m/s and 60m/s isotachs for the corresponding
 359 dates in ERA-i (black contours), and the climatological region of forbidden propagation for linear stationary
 360 Rossby waves (gray stippling).

374 eastward extended jet leads to a better defined waveguide as diagnosed by K_s (Figure 7), as wave-
 375 5 specifically is trapped within the subtropical jet all the way to North America. An additional
 376 effect in these models is a too-weak teleconnection, and the poleward jet shift in these models
 377 is expected to contribute to this too-weak teleconnection, as discussed in Section 2b. However,
 378 these linear diagnostics do not appear capable of explaining why the wavetrain for NCEP extends

FIG. 7. As in Figure 6 but for K in mean state.

379 too far poleward as compared to reanalysis. On the other hand, linear ray tracing does explain this
 380 ability of the wavetrain to reach Alaska. Specifically, figure 8a shows that wave-3 can reach Alaska
 381 using NCEP background winds, while figure 8c shows the wavetrain is confined to midlatitudes if
 382 reanalysis winds are used. The stationary wavenumber does not take into account the meridional
 383 wind while ray tracing does, and to isolate the possible effect of the meridional wind on the ability
 384 of the ray to reach Alaska, we show in figure 8b the rays if zonal winds from NCEP but meridional
 385 winds from ERAi are used. It is clear that propagation to Alaska is weaker than in figure 8a,

³⁸⁶ however there is still more propagation than in figure 8c. Note that this poleward propagation
³⁸⁷ appears to occur on the poleward flank of the forbidden region of wave propagation where wave 3
³⁸⁸ is allowed to propagate (Figure 7a), and therefore the two linear diagnostics do not contradict.

389 FIG. 8. Ray tracing of the extratropical response to wave-3 launched in the boxed region of Figure 5 using the
 390 (top) NCEP simulated winds in week-5 of December initializations; (middle) zonal wind from NCEP and merid-
 391 ional winds from corresponding dates in ERA-I; (bottom) both zonal and meridional winds from corresponding
 392 dates in ERA-I. Rays are launched from the boxed region on Figure 5.

393 The jet in CNRM and CMA is equatorward shifted, and while the theoretical arguments in
 394 Section 2b suggest this should be expected to lead to a stronger teleconnection, the teleconnection
 395 in Figure 1 is actually too weak. Hence the overly weak omega at 500hPa response for both models
 396 (Figure 3) overwhelms any effect from the midlatitude background state. Section 3a noted that
 397 CNRM simulated a RWS of reasonable strength despite an overly weak omega, and this seemingly
 398 paradoxical combination could be reconciled by the southward shift of the jet: a given upper level
 399 divergence can seed a stronger RWS if the jet is too-far south due to a stronger climatological
 400 potential vorticity meridional gradient (as diagnosed by the second term of Equation 1, not shown).
 401 Such a stronger teleconnection for an equatorward shifted jet was found explicitly in both the linear
 402 baroclinic model of Wang et al. (2020b) and the shallow water model of Garfinkel and Hartmann

403 (2010). Hence the extratropical teleconnection of CNRM would likely be even weaker if the jet
404 bias was corrected.

405 Finally, UKMO, ECMWF, and KMA all suffer from relatively small jet biases. However in all
406 three the subtropical jet does not extend far enough eastward, and consistent with this the North
407 Pacific low does not extend far enough eastward to midlatitude North America, but rather is too
408 strong near Alaska (Figure 1). The biases in the subtropical jet and in the location of the North
409 Pacific low are linked, as the waveguide formed by the subtropical jet ends too abruptly in the
410 Central Pacific, while the forbidden region for linear wave propagation ends near the dateline
411 rather than extending further eastward (Figure 7). This effect is demonstrated explicitly using
412 Rossby ray tracing in Supplemental Figure S18: wave-3 launched from the West Pacific is able to
413 reach Alaska using the KMA climatological winds, but not using reanalysis background winds.

414 Overall, the midlatitude basic state leads to biases in teleconnections in all models, though the
415 details of the biases differ among models and cannot be easily generalized.

416 **4. Implications for MJO teleconnections**

417 Stan et al. (2022) recently considered biases in MJO teleconnections in initialized forecasts
418 using the S2S database, and found that teleconnections to the North Pacific were too weak in
419 weeks 2 and 3 in nearly all models. At even earlier lags this too-weak bias goes away and is
420 even reversed to a too-strong bias for some models (Wang et al. 2020a; Stan et al. 2022), but in
421 week-1 the anomalous convection is already incorporated via the initialization. We now revisit the
422 degradation in the North Pacific teleconnection in weeks 2 and 3, and then consider the role of
423 biased tropical convection.

424 Figure 9 shows the geopotential height response lagged three weeks after MJO phase 4/5 as com-
425 pared to phases 8/1. We focus on week-3 and these phases in order to focus on the development
426 of the convective response and the wavetrain, rather than on initializations when the convective
427 response is already present in the West Pacific. Nevertheless, results are similar for MJO phase
428 5/6 as compared to phases 1/2 in week two (Supplemental Figure S19; Stan et al. 2022): MJO
429 phases with enhanced convection in the West Pacific leads to a deepened North Pacific low.
430

431 A trough is present in observations in the North Pacific, but this trough is underestimated by all
432 S2S models (consistent with Stan et al. 2022). This overly-weak teleconnection is, in turn, related
433

424 FIG. 9. As in Figure 1 but for week 3 following NDJF initializations during MJO phases 4/5 as compared to
 425 MJO phases 8/1. The black box is intentionally left in the same location as Figure 3.

436 to biases in the tropics. Goss and Feldstein (2018) and Ting and Held (1990) find that a deeper
 437 North Pacific low occurs about a week after enhanced convection in either the West or Central
 438 tropical Pacific, and hence we focus on the week 2 response in omega at 500hPa in Figure 10. In
 439 reanalysis, the tropical upwelling is present over the Western Pacific and downwelling over the
 440 Indian Ocean, however almost all models miss either the amplitude or the eastward propagation
 441 phase speed of the convection (or both). In NCEP, UKMO, CNRM, and CMA, the zonal dipole
 442 in omega is both too weak and too far to the west. The amplitude is better simulated by BoM and
 443 ECMWF, however the eastward phase speed is too slow (Vitar 2017). In KMA, the amplitude and

432 FIG. 10. As in Figure 3 but for week 2 following NDJF initializations during MJO phases 4/5 as compared to
 433 MJO phases 8/1. The boxes are shifted 35° to the west as compared to Figure 3.

444 phase speed are more reasonable, however the anomalous convection appears to move off of the
 445 equator in both hemispheres.

446 The extratropical response is more sensitive to the anomalous downwelling to the south of Japan
 447 where it seeds the Rossby wave, and this anomalous downwelling is underestimated in most mod-
 448 els in week 2. Even in the few models which represent this subtropical downwelling well in week 2
 449 (e.g. KMA and UKMO), this downwelling is too weak in week 3 (Supplemental Figure 20). Con-
 450 sistent with this, the 200hPa divergence and Rossby wave source anomalies are too weak as well
 451 (Supplemental Figure 21 and 22). Hence the quasi-steady tropical forcing leads to an extratropical
 452 teleconnection that is too-weak, or simply not present, in all models.

453 5. Discussion

454 Thus far we have focused on biases for December initializations, and demonstrated too weak
 455 of a teleconnection in midwinter. In contrast, Chen et al. (2020) find that most CMIP models
 456 systematically simulate too *strong* of an ENSO teleconnection in spring. While some of the S2S

457 models also share this bias, others do not and the multi-model mean is realistic. As an example,
458 Figure 11ab shows the response to ENSO for initializations in February, and can be compared
459 to the comparable Figure 2ab for December initializations. In February, ECMWF simulates too
460 weak a response at later lags while BoM simulates too strong a response (Figure 11ab). In other
461 models differences are not statistically robust (Supplemental Figure S23), and the multi-model
462 mean in week 6 is indistinguishable from the reanalysis response. Hence late winter biases in S2S
463 and in CMIP5 models are not similar. One possible explanation for this difference is that part
464 of the bias in CMIP models arises from SST biases associated with the ocean coupling (e.g. too
465 weak of a decay of ENSO in spring, Liu et al. 2021). However, Chen et al. (2020) and Garfinkel
466 et al. (2019b) found this bias in specified SST simulations of two distinct atmospheric models.
467 It is notable that all S2S models except CMA capture the spring tropical convective response
468 accurately (Figure 11cd), though the subtropical downwelling is stronger for most model than
469 in observations (Figure 11ef). Future work should consider the nature of spring biases in AMIP
470 simulations of additional models.

473 Goss et al. (2018) find that the extratropical response to seasonal-mean vs. time varying convec-
474 tive precipitation occurs due to the same physical mechanisms, and hence the mechanism leading
475 to a North Pacific response to the MJO or to ENSO is generic to the details of how the convec-
476 tive anomalies develop. We find that the extratropical teleconnection response three weeks after
477 MJO phase 4/5 and to ENSO are similar (though with the North Pacific low and North American
478 ridge around 20° further eastward for ENSO; Figure 1 vs. 9), even though the tropical upwelling
479 anomalies are qualitatively different (Figure 3 vs. 10). The tropical upwelling anomalies are less
480 important for the extratropical response than the subtropical upper level divergence and Rossby
481 wave source anomalies, and this subtropical response is more similar between these MJO and
482 ENSO composites. Specifically both ENSO and the MJO feature upper level convergence and
483 subsidence between 20 and 30°N , though the ENSO subsidence is further east by around 35° (Fig-
484 ure 4 and S19). The net effect is a RWS to the south of Japan two weeks after MJO phase 4/5 and
485 over the West/Central Pacific in response to ENSO (Figure 5 and S20). This pronounced zonal
486 shift in the RWS is evident, but much more muted, in geopotential height, likely because linear
487 theory prohibits a North Pacific low response over the West Pacific, and hence the Rossby wave
488 forced by the MJO must first propagate zonally within the subtropical jet before it can effectively

FIG. 11. As in Figure 2 but for initializations in February.

489 propagate meridionally (Seo and Lee 2017). The net effect is that the geopotential height anom-
 490 lies in response to ENSO and the MJO are more similar than the underlying convective anomalies.

491 This paper demonstrated that biases in subtropical downwelling are related to biases in geopo-
 492 tential height on both intraseasonal and seasonal timescales. Biases in subtropical downwelling on
 493 even longer timescales, namely the climatology of each model, were also found to be associated
 494 with biases in climatological stationary waves in Schwartz et al. (2022). Specifically, stronger
 495 subsidence over the subtropical West Pacific is associated with a deeper low in the North Pacific
 496 between 195E and 215E on seasonal mean timescales as well (Figure 9 of Schwartz et al. 2022).

497 These results have implications for the stratospheric response to ENSO. The stratosphere is
 498 particularly sensitive to height variability in the subpolar Northwest Pacific, as troughs in this

471 FIG. 12. As in Figure 2 but for (a-b) Northwest Pacific SSW precursor region, defined as 52-72N, 155-185E
 472 following Garfinkel et al. (2010). (c-d) 100hPa polar cap height response.

499 region can constructively interfere with the climatological stationary waves and reinforce upward
 500 wave propagation into the stratosphere (Garfinkel et al. 2010; Domeisen et al. 2019). Figure 12a-b
 501 focuses on geopotential height anomalies in this region in response to EN as compared to LN, and
 502 demonstrates that in the models the North Pacific low extends to this region (Figure 12a), but in
 503 reanalysis data a ridge occurs in this region at later lags (Figure 12b). This effect is also evident
 504 in Figure 1: the North Pacific low extends too far northwestward towards the Russian coast in
 505 most models (Supplemental Figure S24). Consistent with this bias in height in the subpolar North
 506 Pacific, the polar vortex is weakened in EN relative to LN in five models (ECMWF, UKMO, KMA,
 507 HMCR, and NCEP), but not in reanalysis data over the corresponding period. This divergent polar
 508 vortex response is demonstrated in Figure 12cd: polar cap height is higher for EN at 100hPa
 509 in the models (Figure 12c), but not for the corresponding period in reanalysis data (Figure 12d). A
 510 similar bias in the Northwestern extent of the North Pacific low was also evident for CCMVal2
 511 models in Garfinkel et al. (2012a). Consistent with this bias in the North Pacific low, the S2S and
 512 CCMVal2 models simulate too many SSWs in EN relative to LN (Garfinkel et al. 2012a, 2019a).

513 Vitart (2017) found that MJO teleconnections extended too far to the Northwestern Pacific 11-15
514 days (third pentad) after a strong MJO phase 3, and to a lesser extent also 11-15 days after a strong
515 MJO phase 7. At the lags considered in this work, this bias is no longer present, and rather the
516 MJO teleconnection is too weak (Figure 9).

517 6. Summary

518 ENSO and the MJO dominate the interannual and intraseasonal variability of the tropical Indo-
519 Pacific atmosphere (Madden and Julian 1994; Timmermann et al. 2018; Jiang et al. 2020, and ref-
520 erences therein). Teleconnections of ENSO and the MJO extend to the rest of the world (Taschetto
521 et al. 2020), and form a basis for seasonal climate prediction over North America and East Asia
522 among other regions (Horel and Wallace 1981; Ropelewski and Halpert 1987; Zhang et al. 1996;
523 Shukla et al. 2000; Wang et al. 2000; DeWeaver and Nigam 2004; Brönnimann 2007; Garfinkel
524 et al. 2013; Scaife et al. 2017; Garfinkel et al. 2019b; Domeisen et al. 2019; Weinberger et al.
525 2019). In order for models to actualize the potential predictability associated with ENSO and
526 the MJO, they need to simulate the poleward propagating wavetrain in the North Pacific which
527 is seeded by convective outflow in the tropics. Hence, models need to represent the upper level
528 tropical divergent outflow and subtropical convergence accurately in order to maximize skill. It
529 can be difficult to quantify the robustness of model biases in free-running climate simulations due
530 to unrelated variability and to model biases in other processes. However initialized forecasts of-
531 fer the opportunity to study model biases in teleconnections in which many sources of unrelated
532 variability are relatively minimized.

533 This study tracks the development of North Pacific teleconnections in forecasting models as
534 compared to observations. **In all models examined, the North Pacific low in response to ENSO is**
535 **too weak in the North Pacific, and in most models significantly so. Less than 3% of individual**
536 **ensemble members simulate a response as strong as that observed. In order to understand why**
537 **models struggle with the magnitude of the North Pacific response, we analyzed three** diagnos-
538 tics of tropical outflow and subtropical convergence: the pressure velocity (ω) at 500hPa,
539 divergence at 200hPa, and the Rossby wave source at 200hPa. For most models, there is a clear
540 connection between biases in these three metrics of the tropical response to ENSO/MJO and the
541 subsequent extratropical wave-train. Namely, after the effects of the initialization wear off (a week

542 for the propagating MJO, and a month for the stationary ENSO) the **subtropical downwelling and**
543 **upper level convergence** response to ENSO and the MJO is too weak **in all models**, leading to too
544 weak of an extratropical wavetrain in the North Pacific. **In most models, the tropical upwelling**
545 **response is too weak as well.** For ENSO, this effect is apparent when examining initializations
546 in December before the wavetrain is well established. Future work should consider whether these
547 models can represent the effect of ENSO on the propagation and intensity of the MJO found in
548 observations (Wang and Li 2021).

549 Many models also simulate a North Pacific teleconnection that reaches too far poleward. Such
550 a bias is likely related to biases in the extratropical background state: if the subtropical Pacific
551 jet does not extend far enough eastward (e.g. UKMO, ECMWF, KMA, CNRM and CMA), the
552 extratropical wavetrain is not confined to the waveguide of the jet and spreads poleward. In a few
553 models the subtropical jet is too far equatorward (CNRM, CMA), which in isolation would lead
554 to too-strong teleconnection. However this tendency is compensated by too weak of a tropical
555 divergent outflow at 200hPa, and even for these models the teleconnection is too weak.

556 Despite these biases, the teleconnection is represented in a qualitatively realistic manner by
557 nearly all models. Hence these models are likely already gaining skill from their representation of
558 ENSO and the MJO. However there is a gap between any currently realized skill and the potential
559 skill available, and thus improving the representation of these teleconnections is a pathway for
560 improved model performance. Future work should consider the role of this gap in skill for the
561 signal-to-noise paradox that is apparent in a wide range of subseasonal, seasonal, decadal, and
562 centennial forecasting and projection models (Eade et al. 2014; Scaife and Smith 2018; Baker
563 et al. 2018). While this paradox is commonly associated with the North Atlantic sector, it appears
564 in the North Pacific too (Baker et al. 2018; Scaife and Smith 2018) and has been associated with
565 models being under-sensitive to external forcings and boundary conditions as found here.

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574 *Data availability statement.* The original S2S database is hosted at ECMWF as an extension of
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576 int/datasets/data/s2s/levtype=sfc/type=cf/](http://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/s2s/levtype=sfc/type=cf/). NOAA High Resolution SST data pro-
577 vided by the NOAA/OAR/ESRL PSL, Boulder, Colorado, USA, from their Web site at [https:
578 //psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html#detail](https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html#detail).

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